

A COMPARATIVE INVESTIGATION ON THE UNIAXIAL PLAIN AND NOTCH FATIGUE STRENGTHS OF HEAVY-SECTION CASTINGS MADE OF PEARLITIC AND HIGH-SILICON FERRITIC DUCTILE CAST IRONS

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Ductile cast iron (DCI) finds increasing application in important industrial branches to produce large components. While increasing the component's dimension, the cooling rate generally decreases, thus leading to the formation of casting defects, such as degenerated graphite and shrinkage pores. Different DCI grades can be characterised by different distributions of pores in the material. A change in the dimension, shape and spatial distribution of pores may lead to different behaviours of the materials, thus requiring a change in the designing approach, especially against fatigue failure. In this work, we analyse the fatigue properties of a GJS-600 (pearlitic) and a high silicon content, HSi, (ferritic) grades, emphasising the different features that lead to fatigue failure. We propose a statistical approach to assess the size of the expected critical pore in the vicinity of a notch, which is then combined with a strain energy density (SED)-based fatigue approach to carry out fatigue predictions. The effectiveness of the method is validated using specimens of varying geometries, where fatigue failure is induced by either shrinkage pores or graphite nodules. The proposed approach demonstrates the ability to predict this critical feature, offering valuable insights for designing against fatigue failure in DCI components.

Keywords: Ductile cast iron, Uniaxial fatigue, Shrinkage pores, Highly stressed volume

INTRODUCTION

Ductile cast iron (DCI), also known as nodular cast iron, is increasingly used to produce large castings, employed in several important industrial branches, such as wind energy and cement production. The chemical composition is usually tuned close to the eutectic, thus obtaining low liquidus temperature and superb castability. Nevertheless, large castings, which are characterised by low cooling rates, are generally affected by casting defects, such as degenerated graphite and shrinkage pores. The nucleation of pores can be mitigated by placing chillers in the critical zones, i.e. those affected by very low cooling rates. Nevertheless, up to date, foundries producing large casts struggle in finding ways to reduce or avoid the formation of micro shrinkage porosity. Therefore, it

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is of paramount importance to fully characterise the distribution of defects within the material. Different DCI grades may show different distributions of pores, in terms of size, shape and spatial density. Moreover, the microstructure of the matrix may play a role in influencing the sensitivity of the material to shrinkage pores.

The fatigue properties of a component are also depending on the geometry itself. The presence of notches produces stress intensification, thus decreasing the fatigue limit. Pedranz et al. [1] demonstrated that fatigue failure can be triggered both by shrinkage pores and by notches. In particular, they introduced a novel definition of the highly stressed volume by exploiting a strain energy density (SED)-based approach. A statistical method was then used to assess the size of critical pores expected to be found in such volume. These properties are both material and geometry dependent. The model was validated on experimental uniaxial fatigue tests carried out on notches with different geometries, made of a pearlitic GJS-600 DCI grade.

In this work, we extend the analysis to a ferritic DCI grade, with high silicon content. We generalise the approach for a generic material containing defects (which could be either pores, or inclusions, or other features). We also clarify the procedure necessary to apply this designing approach to mechanical components. In the end, we compare the two analysed DCI grades and point out their characteristics, explaining how, we believe, they should be used to maximise their mechanical response.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The materials investigated in this work are an EN-GJS-600–3 DCI (regarded as GJS-600) with pearlitic matrix and a high silicon content EN-GJS-450–18 DCI (regarded as HSi) with ferritic matrix. The chemical compositions and main mechanical properties of the two DCI grades are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition and main mechanical properties of the investigated DCI grades

	C (%)	Si (%)	Mn (%)	P (%)	S (%)	Cu (%)	Ni (%)	Mg (%)
GJS-600	3.55	2.39	0.28	0.038	0.009	0.52	0.02	0.046
HSi	3.43	3.57	0.19	0.04	0.009	0.06	0.02	0.043
	<i>E</i> (GPa)	<i>G</i> (GPa)	$\sigma_{y,0.2}$ (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	ϵ_{tot} (%)	Poisson's ratio	HB	
GJS-600	174 ± 2	68.5 ± 1.3	363 ± 8	485 ± 15	2.1 ± 0.5	0.27	198 ± 4	
HSi	174 ± 2	68.5 ± 1.3	364 ± 4	476 ± 3	14.4 ± 2.8	0.27	170 ± 2	

Metrological X-ray computed tomography (CT) was exploited to assess the statistical distributions of both graphite nodules and shrinkage pores inside the two investigated DCI grades, analysing a scanned volume $V_0 = 504 \text{ mm}^3$. The analyses were conducted using a Nikon Metrology MCT225 system (Nikon Metrology, UK) characterised by a micro-focus X-ray source (minimum focal spot size equal to 3 μm), 16-bit flat panel detector with 2000×2000 pixel grid, and temperature-

controlled cabinet ($20 \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The voxel size was set equal to $5.8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The obtained CT reconstructions are shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 CT reconstructions of the investigated DCI grades. Shrinkage pores are highlighted, showing the different spatial distributions in the two materials. Colours are related to the pore's volume

Data from CT revealed that: (i) the pearlitic GJS-600 grade is characterised by few, large, shrinkage pores, randomly distributed in the material, (ii) the ferritic HSi grade is characterised by many, smaller pores, homogenously distributed in the material. The CT data were analysed adopting the statistics of the largest extreme value distribution (LEVD) using the Maximum Likelihood Method [2], thus using the following expression, as function of the pore's Feret diameter (d_F):

$$d_F = \lambda + \delta(-\ln(-\ln(F))) \quad (1)$$

Where λ and δ are the shape and scale parameters, respectively, and F is the cumulative probability. The fitted statistical distributions are shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 Statistical distributions of shrinkage pores in the investigated material. The experimental data were collected by CT scans

The CT scans data were also exploited to extract the 3D models of some shrinkage pores, shown in Figure 3. Pores belonging to different materials displayed different morphologies. The HSi grade's pores seem to have a much more intricate and complex shape compared to the GJS-600 grade's pores. At the same Feret diameter, HSi's pores are characterised by a complex shape and a small volume (thus high surface area), while GJS-600's pores are characterised by a smoother shape and a larger volume (thus smaller surface area).

FIGURE 3 3D models of the shrinkage pores reconstructed using the data collected by CT scans, for the two investigated DCI grades

The pore's 3D reconstructions were used to create finite element models, where single pores were randomly rotated and placed in a plain specimen with 14 mm diameter. The same approach was already presented in one of our previous works for the GJS-600 grade [1]. In this work we integrate the analysis with the data related to the HSi grade. The finite element models were analysed adopting a strain energy density (SED)-based approach, to evaluate the influence of pores on the fatigue properties of the material. The approach is accurately explained in our previous work [1]. In brief, the model is meshed, loaded with unitary stress and solved. Then, the SED is evaluated over a spherical control volume placed at the local stress maxima around the pore. The procedure is iterated until the whole surface of the pore is covered. The maximum evaluated SED, regarded as SED_{max} , is taken as representative of the analysed pore and used to calculate the pore's fatigue stress concentration factor $K_{f,P}$, according to the following expression:

$$K_{f,P} = \sqrt{\frac{SED_{max}}{SED_{nominal}}} = \sqrt{\frac{SED_{max}}{\frac{\sigma_{nominal}^2}{2E}}} \quad (2)$$

Where $\sigma_{nominal} = 1$ MPa is the applied unitary nominal stress, and E is the elastic modulus. The procedure used to determinate the SED control radius is accurately explained by Benedetti et al. [3]–[5] and consists in testing two notches with different severities (for instance a sharp V-notch and a blunt V-notch) under fatigue loading. The fatigue data are then used to evaluate both the intrinsic fatigue strength of the material (fatigue curve of the pore-free material) and the SED control radius.

The results of the finite element models are shown in Figure 4 as function of the analysed material and the Feret diameter of the pore. The data were then fitted according to the following formula, similar to the one proposed by Murakami [6]:

$$K_{f,P} = \left(\frac{d_{F,pore}}{d_{F,nodule}} \right)^Y \quad (3)$$

Where $d_{F,pore}$ is the pore's Feret diameter, $d_{F,nodule}$ is the graphite nodules mean Feret diameter, and γ is a fitting parameter. $d_{F,nodule}$ was assessed by analyzing the data coming from the CT scans and is equal to 160 μm for the GJS-600 grade, and 67 μm for the HSi grade. When $d_{F,pore} = d_{F,nodule}$ the pore is considered irrelevant.

FIGURE 4 Fatigue stress concentration factor as function of the pore's size, for the two investigated materials. The data are obtained through finite element simulations

The finite element simulations show that the HSi grade is considerably less sensitive to shrinkage pores compared to the GJS-600 grade. This phenomenon is explained by two main reasons: (i) the SED control radius of the HSi grade is larger than the GJS-600's one, making the material generally less sensitive to geometrical discontinuities. This is reasonable, as the ferritic matrix is characterised by a ductile behaviour, as confirmed by the elongation at brake reported in Table 1, (ii) the peculiar morphology of HSi grade's shrinkage pores, characterised by a large surface area and small volume, is producing less severe stress intensification, thus decreasing the impact of pores on the fatigue properties of the material. The main fatigue properties and characteristic features of the investigated materials are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2 Main fatigue properties and characteristic features of the investigated materials

	GJS-600	HSi
Intrinsic fatigue limit, σ_{f1}^*	277 MPa	205 MPa
Plain fatigue limit, σ_{f1}	161 ± 10 MPa	183 ± 14 MPa
R_1	0.15 mm	0.25 mm
Notch sensitivity	High	Low
Sensitivity to pores	High	Low

PROPOSED DESIGNING APPROACH

The data and equations presented in the previous Section can be used to assess the fatigue limit of the two DCI grades once the pore's Feret diameter is known. Nevertheless, when dealing with notches, the determination of the expected pore's size is not straightforward. Exploiting the largest extreme value distribution fitted on the CT scans data, it is possible to predict the expected pore size in a given volume V , as function of the cumulative probability F [1]:

$$d_F(F, V) = \left[\lambda + \delta \left(-\ln(-\ln(F)) \right) \right] \cdot \chi_0 \quad (4)$$

$$\chi_0 = \begin{cases} \frac{d_F(F, V)}{d_F\left(\frac{V}{V_0}\right)} & V \leq V_0 \\ \frac{d_F\left(\frac{V_0}{V}\right)}{d_F(F, V)} & V > V_0 \end{cases}$$

Where V_0 is the scanned volume in the CT analyses. V can generally be regarded as the highly stressed volume (HSV) and, according to the original formulation, is defined as the volume of material, in the vicinity of a notch, subjected to a stress equal or higher than $n\%$ of the peak stress at the notch (where $n\%$ varies from 80 % to 95 %, in the literature). In [1], we introduced a new definition of the HSV, called energy based HSV (EB-HSV). In the new definition, the HSV is defined in a precise way, without the need of setting semi-empirical parameters (like the $n\%$ present in the original definition), as the volume of material subjected to a stress equal or higher than the peak stress of the notch divided by the $K_{f,p}$ of the critical pore expected to be found in the EB-HSV. As $K_{f,p}$ is function of the pore's size, which is function of the EB-HSV (V), which is in turn function of $K_{f,p}$, the procedure to calculate these quantities is iterated till convergence (usually reached in a few iterations). Figure 5 shows the predicted fatigue limit, which is equal to $\sigma_{fl}^* / K_{f,p}$, as function of the EB-HSV, calculated for a cumulative probability $F = 99\%$. The higher the EB-HSV, the larger the expected critical pore found in such volume, therefore, the higher the $K_{f,p}$. It can be observed that, according to our predictions, when the highly stressed volume is quite large (EB-HSV $> 60 \text{ mm}^3$), the fatigue limit of the ferritic HSi grade becomes higher than the fatigue limit of the pearlitic GJS-600 grade. This behaviour may seem counterintuitive, due to the high intrinsic fatigue strength of the GJS-600 grade. Nevertheless, the high sensitivity of the pearlitic matrix to pores, explain this strong influence on the pore's size.

In Figure 5 we also indicate the predictions of the fatigue limit of plain specimens with 14 mm diameter and 50 mm gauge length, thus corresponding to an EB-HSV of 7696.9 mm^3 . The predictions can be compared to the plain fatigue limits reported in Table 2. The committed error is -1.2 % for the GJS-600 grade and -2.6 % for the HSi grade.

The model presented until this point only deals with the effect of shrinkage pores on the fatigue properties. Although the effect of the notch is considered while assessing the EB-HSV, the direct influence that the notch has on the fatigue behaviour of the component is not taken into account. To overpass this problem, the notch fatigue stress concentration factor $K_{f,N}$ is introduced. $K_{f,N}$ is calculated by exploiting the SED-based fatigue method presented by Pedranz et al. [7]. In brief, a finite element model of the notch is created and simulated applying a unitary nominal stress. The SED is assessed at the notch root. $K_{f,N}$ is then calculated according to the following equation:

FIGURE 5 Fatigue limit of the material, containing shrinkage pores, as function of the highly stressed volume EB-HSV

$$K_{f,N} = \sqrt{\frac{SED_{notch}}{SED_{nominal}}} = \sqrt{\frac{SED_{notch}}{\frac{\sigma_{nominal}^2}{2E}}} \quad (5)$$

The fatigue stress concentration factors of the notch and the pore can then be compared. We hypothesise that the higher one will control fatigue failure, thus leading to either a notch-dominated or a pore-dominated failure. Therefore, the fatigue strength of the notch can be assessed according to the following equation:

$$\sigma_{fl,N} = \min \left\{ \frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,N}}, \frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,P}} \right\} \quad (6)$$

VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

To better explain the proposed approach, we present, in this section, some predictions carried out on cylindrical V-notched specimens with variable notch opening angle. By varying the notch opening angle, the highly stressed volume varies consequently. We also provide some experimental results, obtained by testing both materials. Nevertheless, at the moment, HSi grade's data are available only for a notch opening angle of 60° and plain specimens. The technical drawing of the specimens with variable notch opening angle is shown in Figure 6.

The notch opening angle $2\bar{\alpha}$ varies from 60° to 180° (which represents a plain specimen), while the notch radius is kept constant and equal to 0.2 mm.

FIGURE 6 Technical drawing of the specimens with variable notch opening angle, tested under uniaxial fatigue. Dimensions are in millimetres

The procedure to follow in order to assess the fatigue strength of a notch is the following:

- i. calculate the EB-HSV, the corresponding pore size d_F and the corresponding $K_{f,P}$;
- ii. calculate the notch fatigue stress concentration factor $K_{f,N}$;
- iii. calculate the fatigue limit of the notch as $\sigma_{fl,N} = \min \left\{ \frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,N}}, \frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,P}} \right\}$.

Figure 7 shows a plot in which the effect of the notch and the effect of pores are directly compared, as function of the notch opening angle and for the two investigated materials. The black dots represent $\frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,N}}$, thus accounting only for the effect of the notch on the fatigue properties. The solid lines represent $\frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,P}}$, which directly depends on the EB-HSV and thus the critical pore's size. As shown by the red arrows, when $\frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,N}} > \frac{\sigma_{fl}^*}{K_{f,P}}$ fatigue failure becomes pore-dominated and, therefore, the fatigue limit has to be decreased, thus accounting for the presence of critical shrinkage pores.

FIGURE 7 Fatigue predictions as function of the notch opening angle of the specimen, considering failure to be notch-dominated (black dots) or pore-dominated (red dots). As indicated by the red arrows, the lowest fatigue resistance between the two cases is considered as representative of the specimen's behaviour

It can be observed that the two materials display a different behaviour. In particular, the GJS-600 grade show a transition from notch-dominated to pore-dominated fatigue failure at 164°, while the failure in the HSi grade becomes pore-dominated only in plain specimens, or, generally speaking, in very blunt notches, characterised by an extremely large EB-HSV. The predictions are compared to the available experimental results in Figure 8.

FIGURE 8 Fatigue predictions (dashed line) as function of the notch opening angle, for the two DCI grades investigated in this work. The coloured bands represent the variation of pore-dominated predictions when the cumulative probability F ranges from 90 % to 99 %

The proposed model accurately predicts the experimental data. Moreover, for large opening angles, close to 180°, the HSi grade shows the highest fatigue resistance. In this range, the failure is thought to be pore-dominated for both materials. Nevertheless, the influence of pores in the HSi grade is much lower compared to the GJS-600 grade. At lower notch opening angles, thus lower EB-HSV, the GJS-600 grade can exploit its higher intrinsic fatigue strength, thus displaying a higher

fatigue resistance compared to the HSi grade. The predictions carried out for the HSi grade at 160° notch opening angle display a higher error compared to other opening angles. This may be due to the large experimental scatter of this fatigue curve (as indicated by the scatter band Figure 8). Nevertheless, fatigue predictions are conservative. To further investigate the problem, SEM fractographic analyses will be carried out on the tested specimens.

The predictions and experimental results presented in this work may indicate that the two DCI grades could be suitable to produce different types of components. To fully exploit the material's mechanical properties, the GJS-600 grade should be used to produce smaller components, characterised by sharp notches and low highly stressed volumes. On the contrary, the HSi grade seems to be more suitable to produce large components, characterised by blunt notches and large highly stressed volumes. Moreover, the extremely low sensitivity to pores of the HSi grade makes this material more reliable and less unpredictable.

In support of the predictions and experimental results, the fracture surface of some specimens made of GJS-600 are shown in Figure 9. The SEM fractographic analysis confirms that, for the GJS-600 grade, the transition from notch-dominated to pore-dominated fatigue failure is between 160° and 170° notch opening angle, as the proposed model predicts.

FIGURE 8 SEM fracture surfaces of different notch opening angle specimens made of the GJS-600 grade

CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE WORK

This work highlights the fatigue behaviour of two DCI grades, namely a EN-GJS-600-3, with pearlitic matrix, and a high silicon content EN-GJS-450-18, with ferritic matrix. The materials were analysed exploiting X-ray computed tomography and fatigue testing. CT analyses revealed different

properties of shrinkage pores as function of the material. The GJS-600 grade contains a few, large, pores, randomly distributed within the material. The HSi grade contains a much larger number of smaller pores, more homogeneously distributed within the material. Moreover, the morphology of pores in the HSi grade is characterised by a more intricate shape, with a larger surface area and a smaller volume. The approach proposed in this work joins extreme value statistics, the concept of energy based highly stressed volume, and a SED-based method, to carry out fatigue predictions on notched components. The approach accounts for the presence of shrinkage pores in the material, and their possible interaction, on a statistical point of view, with the notch. Depending on the severity of the notch and the critical pore size, the approach predicts either a notch-dominated or pore-dominated fatigue failure.

This method was validated on experimental data collected by testing cylindrical V-notched specimens with variable opening angle. The predictions are accurate in terms of fatigue limit and point of transition from a notch-dominated to a pore-dominated failure. Nevertheless, some experimental data regarding the HSi grade are still missing (between 60° and 140° notch opening angles). We plan to carry out more fatigue tests to investigate the effect of the notch opening angle in this material, thus completely validating the proposed approach.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

$2\bar{\alpha}$	Notch opening angle
E	Young's modulus
G	Shear modulus
$\sigma_{y,0.2}$	Yield strength
UTS	Ultimate tensile strength
ε_{tot}	Strain at failure
HB	Brinell hardness
V_0	Scanned volume in CT scans
V	Highly stressed volume
d_F	Feret diameter
λ	Shape parameter of the pores' statistical distribution
δ	Scale parameter of the pores' statistical distribution
F	Cumulative probability
$K_{f,P}$	Pore fatigue stress concentration factor
γ	Fitting parameter that correlates $K_{f,P}$ to d_F
R_1	Mode I SED control radius
χ_0	Volume scaling factor
HSV	Highly stressed volume
EB-HSV	Energy based highly stressed volume

σ_{fl}^*	Intrinsic fatigue limit
$K_{f,N}$	Notch fatigue stress concentration factor

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